

Site: ^{SPHINX} TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number (4f)

Progress of Excavation 4/II 180. (4f) first considered part of (6b) but separation line noted (see entry under (6b). Removed separately from (6b) but some mixing may have occurred. (4f), like (4e) may be only bottoming out of (4d)

Locus Description BROWN DAMP slightly clay-like soil

Location in Square Against (6b) and bedrock ledge and floor of sheathing socket

Under Locus (4e) Over Locus (6b) & BEDROCK FLOOR

Locus Dimensions 7.68 - 7.69 surface

Levels ↓

Analysis of non-artifactual materials Concentration of loose large charcoal frags just above bedrock bottom of deposit. Fine to middling sized limestone material, few small frags granite, alabaster.